

FAILURE MECHANISMS IN CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED PEEK

P.J.Hine
Armstrong Patents
Manor Lane
Skipton Road
York
UK

B.Brew
R.A.Duckett
I.M.Ward
Department of Physics
University of Leeds
Leeds LS2 9JT
UK

ABSTRACT

Results are presented for fracture toughness tests on unidirectional carbon fibre PEEK composites. Both interlaminar and intralaminar fracture behaviour were examined using double cantilever beam specimens, and intralaminar fracture was also studied using single edge notch samples testing in bending at both low strain rate and impact rates. It was concluded that the very high fracture toughness of this composite relates to the combination of high matrix toughness and strong fibre/matrix bonding.

INTRODUCTION

In the search for a high performance composite material recent research has concentrated on improving the toughness of the matrix phase. This has proceeded in two distinct directions, first by the modification of an existing matrix, usually a thermoset: examples of this can be found in references [1-3]. The second approach has been to develop a new range of composites employing a thermoplastic matrix which is inherently more tough. Examples include polyimide/amide [4], polyethylene terephthalate [5], polypropylene [6], poly(phenylene sulphide) [7] and poly(ether etherketone) (PEEK) [8].

The work reported here has followed the second route and has been concerned with fracture tests on continuous carbon fibre (AS4) reinforced

PEEK. Tests have been developed to characterise their fracture properties and to identify the major energy absorbing mechanisms by linking macroscopic toughness measurements with analysis of the failure surfaces.

EXPERIMENTAL

Most tests were carried out on unidirectional panels of material made by laying up prepreg tapes of AS4/PEEK. Cracks were propagated parallel to the three principal planes, concentrating on the two weaker planes containing the fibre direction. The two geometries used were the double cantilever beam (DCB) and the single edge notch sample tested in bending (SEN). With the DCB geometry it was possible to examine both interlaminar fracture, where the plane of the crack was parallel to the individual laminates (DCB1), and intralaminar fracture where the plane of the crack was perpendicular to the laminates (DCB2). For the DCB1 geometry a notch was formed by moulding a piece of aluminium foil between the central two plies. For the DCB2 geometry a notch was made by sawing and then sharpening the notch with a razor blade.

The SEN geometry was used for tests both at a slow strain rate on a tensile test machine, and at impact rates on an instrumented Charpy test machine. The plane of the crack was perpendicular to the individual laminates (intralaminar) so that the notching procedure was similar to that described above for the DCB2 geometry.

THEORY

The fracture mechanics parameters G_c and K_{Ic} were used to characterise the toughness of the composite. Two distinct forms of crack propagation were observed, termed unstable and stable. In stable crack propagation the crack initiated and then travelled across the sample at a speed governed by the testing conditions. For such behaviour the strain energy release rate G_c was calculated from the Irwin-Kies equation: the value obtained was then indicative of the propagation stage of fracture.

For unstable fracture the crack, travelled across the sample and then arrested if the sample was wide enough. For this type of fracture behaviour G_c , again calculated from Irwin-Kies, was determined from, and so reflected, the points of crack initiation and arrest.

The calculation of the stress intensity factor K_{Ic} was determined in a similar way for both stable and unstable fracture. For an isotropic material the effect of the sample geometry on the stress field at the crack tip is allowed for by the finite width correction factor Y . For an anisotropic material values of Y have to be recalculated to account for the changes to the crack tip stress field caused by the orthotropic material properties. This has been accomplished following Sweeney [9], using a finite element package (PAFEC) to calculate the stress field and hence the orthotropic finite width correction factor Y_o . For the SEN geometry both Y and Y_o depend on crack length but the difference between them stays constant at about 10%. For the DCB geometry Y and Y_o are independent of crack length, the difference between the two values being a factor of 3. Hence values for K_{Ic} for the two tests, calculated from the isotropic value Y , were found to differ greatly whereas values of K_{Ic} calculated from the orthotropic factor Y_o were found to agree very well.

RESULTS

a) DCBI - Interlaminar fracture -For this testing geometry three types of crack propagation were seen. The samples failed either in a completely stable manner, or by a combination of stable and unstable fracture, or in a few cases by purely unstable fracture.

For purely stable fracture the crack travelled slowly across the sample at a speed governed by the crosshead speed of the test. After a small rise at low crack lengths, due to growth of a damage zone at the crack tip, the value of G was independent of crack length with relatively little scatter.^c Values for G_c and K_c , for stable fracture, are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

G_c (kJ/m^2) and K_c ($\text{MNm}^{-3/2}$) for the DCBI specimen geometry

Failure Mode	G_c	G_c^I	G_c^A	K_c	K_c^I	K_c^A
	(stable)	(unstable)		(stable)	(unstable)	
All stable	1.93±0.05			5.20±0.06		
Stable/unstable	1.93±0.05	1.96±0.05	0.725±0.08	5.20±0.06	5.25±0.15	3.19±0.32
All unstable		1.79±0.07	1.12±0.07		4.86±0.19	3.82±0.27

For the few samples that showed purely unstable fracture the crack travelled across the sample in a series of jumps between 5 mm and 20 mm in length. G_c and K_c were calculated for both crack initiation and crack arrest and the values are shown in Table 1. There was more scatter in these values compared to those for stable fracture because the result is dependent on the point of crack initiation and hence on the reproducibility of the starter notch.

The third type of fracture behaviour seen in the DCBI samples was a mixture of stable and unstable fracture. A schematic plot of this type of failure is shown in Figure 1. It is seen that after a period of stable fracture the crack suddenly accelerates giving rise to a burst of unstable crack propagation. The transition in fracture behaviour was associated with a rise in G_c such that the point of fast fracture initiation always occurred at a higher value of G_c than the stable value.

This form of behaviour is indicative that crack tip blunting is occurring at the crack tip, causing the rise in the measured toughness. Average toughness values, for both G_c and K_{Ic} and for both components of this fracture mode, are given in Table 1.

The damage caused by the propagation of the main crack was confined to a very small region either side of the fracture plane. Examination of the fracture surface showed very little fibre disturbance or fibre breakage for interlaminar fracture. The fibres that were exposed showed a fine layer of deformed PEEK on their surface: no evidence was found for failure at the fibre/matrix interface indicating very strong fibre/matrix adhesion.

Figure 1. A schematic diagram showing the rise in G_c prior to unstable fracture

The locus of failure was further investigated by taking a polished section at right angles to the main crack plane. This showed that although the initial crack had been started in an interlaminar region, the final failure travelled down the centre of an adjacent laminate. This is a consequence of the ductile matrix being quite tough, making the fibre rich regions more favourable for propagation.

The fracture surfaces were dominated by the microyielding of the matrix phase. For stable fracture this was very extensive whereas for unstable fracture it was on a much smaller scale. From the observations up to this point it is apparent that for interlaminar fracture (DCB1) the toughness of the composite is mainly derived from the deformation of the matrix phase.

b) DCB2 - Intralaminar

For this testing geometry only one form of crack propagation was observed: this was always a mixture of stable and unstable fracture. For crack propagation perpendicular to the laminates G_c and K_c rose with crack length as shown in Figure 2. The values at low crack lengths were similar to those seen for interlaminar fracture and so this rise in toughness is an extra toughening effect due to the direction of crack propagation. The toughening was caused by extra fibres bridging between the cracked faces, increasing the toughness so that as the fibre bridging developed with crack length the toughness rose. This is a consequence of some misorientation of the individual laminates. This mechanism is not as apparent for interlaminar crack propagation because of the good alignment of the fibres.

The contribution of fibre bridging for this mode of crack propagation is in effect a form of crack tip blunting which causes the occasional transition from stable to unstable propagation. A summary of the results from the DCB2 geometry are shown in Table 2.

The fracture surfaces, as would be expected, showed much more fibre disturbance and fibre breakage than for the DCB1 samples, and so an increase in the damage zone. Stable crack propagation was again associated with widespread microductility of the matrix phase whereas the unstable fracture surfaces showed much reduced ductility. No failure at the fibre/matrix interface was observed.

Figure 2. Typical results from DCB2 tests showing the build up of G_c with crack length

TABLE 2

G_c (kJ/m^2) and K_c ($\text{MNm}^{-3/2}$) for the DCB2 geometry

Failure Mode	G_c	G_c^I	G_c^A	K_c	K_c^I	K_c^A
	stable	unstable		stable	unstable	
Stable/ unstable	2.00 2.60	2.64±0.30	1.45±0.40	5.20 5.70	5.80±0.30	4.29±1.20

c) SEN - Intralaminar

i) Slow rate - G_c and K_c were found to be independent of crack length although this was for crack propagation perpendicular to the individual laminates. This is because by the width of the sample is not wide enough to allow for fibre bridging to become established. In effect this is similar to the DCB2 samples at low crack lengths, and for the DCB1 samples over their whole length.

There were some samples that showed stable fracture at the crack tip. Others showed unstable fracture from the crack tip, when unstable fracture initiated from the crack tip it always travelled completely across the sample. A summary of the results for the SEN test at a slow rate is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3

G_c (kJ/m^2) and K_c ($\text{MNm}^{3/2}$) for the three point bend geometry at slow and impact strain rates

Strain rate	Failure mode	G_c	G_c^I	K_c^I
		stable	unstable	unstable
slow	stable/unstable	2.05±0.20		3.72±0.11
	all unstable		1.36±0.09	3.72±0.11
impact	all unstable		1.32±0.13	4.26±0.40

ii) Impact - All the samples tested in impact failed in a completely unstable manner with a lower value of G_c than seen at lower strain rates. Raising the strain rate has the usual effect of reducing the ductility

and the toughness G_c and thus has the effect of suppressing the stable mode of crack propagation. This is a further indication that stable fracture and matrix ductility are strongly linked. The results from the impact tests are shown in Table 3.

The results from the three samples geometries, shown in Table 1, 2 and 3 show good consistency between the calculated values of G_c and K_c . The values obtained are geometry independent suggesting the correct implementation of fracture mechanics. A further check on consistency can be made by comparing the values of K_c and G_c for each test. Sih et al [10] have shown that for an orthotropic material

$$K_c^2 = E_o G_c \quad (1)$$

E_o is termed the orthotropic modulus and is given by

$$\frac{1}{E_o} = \left(\frac{S_{11}S_{22}}{2} \left(\left(\frac{S_{22}}{S_{11}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{2S_{12} + S_{66}}{2S_{11}} \right) \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where S_{ij} are the compliance constants. From the material properties given in Table 1 the orthotropic modulus was calculated to be 11.9 ± 0.9 GPa. It is then possible to compare the values of K_c and G_c through equation (1) for each pair of values in Tables 1, 2, and 3 by calculating a value for $E_o G_c / K_c^2$. The mean value of this ratio is found to be 0.93 ± 0.03 . It is encouraging that the mean value is close to unity and further emphasises the validity of the application of fracture mechanics to this system.

CONCLUSIONS

The two important properties which govern the behaviour of the carbon fibre-PEEK composites are the tough ductile matrix and the strong fibre/matrix bond. The two factors ensure that the damage is restricted to either side of the main crack front and that there is a very high value of toughness in comparison to other composite systems, based on a thermosetting matrix. In the absence of fibre bridging the evidence from surface analysis shows that the toughness is mostly determined by the energy to deform plastically the matrix phase.

For interlaminar crack propagation G_c and K_c were found to be geometry independent and related through the orthotropic modulus. Although initiated in an interlaminar region the final crack propagation occurred in a fibre rich region of an adjacent laminate. Crack tip blunting occurred as a consequence of tougher regions in the path of the crack, causing a transition from stable to unstable crack propagation.

For intralaminar fracture the mechanism of fibre bridging imparted additional toughness and increased stability, confirming the importance of matrix ductility in the behaviour of the carbon fibre-PEEK material.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

P.J.Hine and B.Brew were supported by an ICI JRS scheme. We are grateful for discussion and help from ICI, in particular D.R.Carlile, D.C.Leach, D.R.Moore and F.M.Willmouth.

REFERENCES

1. Penn, L., Morra B. and Mowes, E., A rubberized epoxy system for filament winding. Composites, 1977, 8, 23
2. Scott, J.M. and Phillips D.C., Carbon fibre composites with rubber toughened matrices. J.Mater.Sci., 1975 10, 551
3. Bucknall, C.B. and Partridge, D.K., Effects of morphology in the epoxy/PES matrix on the fatigue behaviour of uniaxial CFRP. Composites, 1984, 15, 129
4. Curtis, P.J., Bader, M.G. and Bailey, J.E., The stiffness and strength of a polyamide thermoplastic reinforced with glass and carbon fibres. J.Mater.Sci., 1978, 13 377
5. Lhymn, C. and Schultz, J.M., Fracture behaviour of collimated thermoplastic poly(ethylene terephthalate) reinforced with short E-glass fibre. J.Mater.Sci., 1983, 18, 2029
6. Ramsteiner, F. and Theysohn, R., Tensile and impact strengths of unidirectional short fibre-reinforced thermoplastics. Composites, 1979, 10, 111
7. Buckley, L.J., Schaffer, I. and Trabocco, R.E., Physical and mechanical properties of conductive composites. SAMPE Quarterly, 1984, 15, 1
8. Cogswell, F.N. and Hopprich, M., Environmental resistance of carbon fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone. Composites, 1983, 14, 251
9. Sweeney, J., Finite-width correction factors for SEN testing of orthotropic materials in opening mode. J.Strain Analysis, 1986, 21, 99
10. Sih, G.C., Paris, P.C. and Irwin, G.P., On cracks in rectilinearly anisotropic bodies. Int.J.Frac.Mechs, 1965, 1 189